

Selective Dehydrogenation of n-heptane on Chromia-alumina Catalyst**

A. JAIN and K. A. VENKATACHALAM*

Petrochem. Laboratory, Laxminarayan Institute of Technology, Nagpur

Manuscript received 24 April 1978, accepted 2 October 1978

Surface acidity modifiers such as n-butylamine (BA), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF), furfural (FR), and propylmercaptan (PM) used alone or as mixtures in the concentration range 0.000 to 0.125 g. atoms nonhydrocarbon element in 100 ml feed of n-heptane were studied for dehydrogenation of n-heptane on chromia-alumina catalyst (20% Cr₂O₃ on γ -alumina) at 500° and space velocity of 2hr⁻¹. These suppressed the aromatisation of n-heptane. The addition of the above surface acidity modifiers improved the selectivity of the catalysts, defined as olefin/(olefin + aromatic) in the catalyzate, which improved from 0.49 for no modifier to 0.56 to 1.0 for modifiers PM, BA, DMSO, FR and DMF. While others did not affect the intrinsic activity of the catalyst, PM was found to poison it. This poisoning effect, however, could be reduced when FR was added to PM.

CATALYTIC dehydrogenation of n-paraffins for the production of higher (>C₆) olefins has attracted attention¹ on account of the possibility of n-paraffin resources being available due to development of molecular sieves for the separation of n-paraffins from petroleum fractions²⁻⁴. The Pacol process⁵ developed by UOP is an example of industrial development in this field. The catalyst used in this process has not been disclosed. The possibility of using well known industrial catalysts such as chromia-alumina, molybdena-alumina etc. for selective n-paraffin dehydrogenation has been investigated by a few workers⁶⁻¹⁰. In this connection Shuilkin and coworkers¹¹ have studied the effect of variation in the methods of preparation of chromia-alumina catalyst, introduction of alkaline additives etc. As has been shown recently addition of alkaline oxides to chromia-alumina catalyst may cause more rapid deactivation of the catalyst¹² or decrease its thermal stability¹³. Improvement of dehydrogenation selectivity of a bifunctional catalyst such as chromia-alumina probably requires adjustment of concentration of surface acidic centers to minimise aromatization of olefins and n-paraffin cracking. The possibility of achieving this object by introducing suitable quantities of various surface acidity modifiers in the feed does not seem to have been investigated so far. Such a technique is probably free from the disadvantages mentioned above. In this article are presented the results of such an attempt to improve n-heptane dehydrogenation selectivity of industrial chromia-alumina catalyst.

Experimental

Experiments were carried out in a fixed bed pyrex glass tubular reactor (43.3×5 cms.) kept in an electrically heated glass jacket. Reaction temperatures were measured by chromel-alumel thermocouple inserted in an axial thermowell (43.3×0.25 cm). Catalyst (33 ml.) was held in the central uniform temperature region of the reactor; silica chips and pyrex glass tubings (2.5×0.5

cms.) were used to fill the remaining reactor space. Liquid feed was introduced at the desired rate by a balandin burette. Reactions took place at atmospheric pressure without any added hydrogen. Liquid effluents were condensed by ice cold water and gases measured by a Toshniwal gas flow meter. Chromia-alumina catalyst (W.G. Grace & Co.) was used and had the following characteristics. Compn. 20% Cr₂O₃ on γ -Alumina-base, bulk density 0.8 gms/ml., olive green spheres of average diameter 0.4 mm. All runs were of 110-140 minutes and gave sufficient long period of constant activity. Catalyst was regenerated at the end of each run at 450° in a current of dry air for 1.5 hr.

Catalytic conversion of solutions of n-heptane (VEB) containing n-butylamine (BA) (Riedel), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) (Kochlight), dimethylformamide (DMF) (E-merk), furfural (FR) (BDH), Propylmercaptan (PM) (Schuchardt Munchen) either alone or as mixture in the concentration range 0.0-0.125 g-atom of nonhydrocarbon element (nhe)/100 ml. of feed was studied. It was verified that the physical constants of the compounds agreed reasonably well with the literature values. Only furfural was distilled before use. Most of the experiments were carried out at 500°, space velocity 2 hr⁻¹. The possibility of catalytic decomposition of nonhydrocarbon compounds alone was investigated by passing benzene solutions of the compounds across the catalyst at 500° and space velocity 2 hr⁻¹.

Feed solutions and catalyzate were analyzed for olefins and aromatic contents by determination of bromine number and percent sulphonation as per ASTM/IP¹⁴ methods.

Results and Discussion

Table-1 gives typical results of experiments carried out to study the possibility of catalytic decomposition

** Presented at the National Symposium on Catalysis held at I.I.T. Kharagpur, Dec. 29-31, 1975
* For correspondence.

TABLE-1. CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF VARIOUS NONHYDROCARBON COMPOUNDS.

Feed : Solutions in Benzene.
Temp. : 500°C. ; Space velocity 2 hr⁻¹.

Run No.	68	69	70	71
Comp. of Soln*	—	1.9 ml. FR	3.2ml.FR + 2.6ml.PM	1.9ml. DMSO
g of nhe/100ml feed.	0.0	0.7	2.2	1.19
Bromine number of catalyzate	0.331	0.781	0.808	0.844
Volume of catalyzate (% vol. feed) expected.				
a)	90.8	90.9	91.3	90.9
b)	90.8	89.0	85.5	89.0
Experimental	90.8	88.5	86.5	88.0

* denotes here & in all other Tables, ml-nhc/100 ml. feed a—when nhc collect in the catalyzate undecomposed.
b) When nhc compounds are completely decomposed to gaseous products.

For both a & b it is assumed that the fraction of feed benzene appearing in the catalyzate in runs 69, 70 and 71 would be the same as in run 68.

of the nonhydrocarbon compounds (nhc) used. It is seen that the bromine number of the catalyzate is less than 1, which is within the error in the determination of bromine number. The contribution to bromine absorbing compounds in the catalyzate on account of thermal and catalytic decomposition of the nhc can therefore be ignored. The last rows in Table-1 indicate that the nhc compounds probably undergo significant decomposition to gaseous products.

Mole fraction n-heptane converted to olefin and aromatics in the various runs was therefore calculated from the bromine number and percent sulphonation values by assuming the olefins to be heptene and aromatics to be toluene and for three cases :

- The nhc collect in the catalyzate and get completely sulphonated ; after correcting the sulphonation values, calculations may be made as if the feed were pure n-heptane.
- The compounds collect in the catalyzate, and
- Get completely decomposed to gaseous products ; but composition of the solution is taken into consideration for calculations. The results of

such calculations for a typical case are given in Table-2. It is seen that calculations for all the three cases give the same results. Calculation as for case (a) was therefore used in all runs.

TABLE-2. CALCULATION OF n-HEPTANE CONVERSION.

Comp. of Soln. : (2.25 ml. DMSO + 1.8 ml. FR)
Temperature 500°C : Space velocity 2 hr⁻¹.

Conversion [†]	a	b	c
Olefins	0.063	0.065	0.065
Aromatics	0.002	0.002	0.003

[†] Here and in all other Tables, mole fraction of n-heptane converted to olefins & aromatics.

A set of initial experiments was carried out to choose the optimum temperature and space velocity, yielding the maximum conversion of pure n-heptane to olefins on the given sample of chromia-alumina catalyst. Results are given in Table-3. In these experiments space velocity was varied by changing the volume of the catalyzate. It is seen from Table-3, that yield of olefins is highest at 500° and space velocity 2hr⁻¹.

TABLE-3. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND SPACE VELOCITY IN CONVERSION OF n-HEPTANE

Temp. °C.	Space velocity hr ⁻¹ .	Conversion	Olefin	Aromatics	Selectivity
475	2	0.037	0.075	0.33	
500	1	0.066	0.056	0.54	
	2	0.082	0.101	0.45	
	4	0.048	0.028	0.63	
525	2	0.068	0.106	0.39	

Table-3 also gives the variation with kinetic parameters of dehydrogenation selectivity of the catalyst defined as below :

$$\text{Selectivity} = \left(\frac{\text{olefin}}{\text{Olefin} + \text{Aromatic}} \right) \text{ in the catalyzate.}$$

It is seen that selectivity under condition of maximum olefin yield, is improved 1.4 times by changing kinetic parameters, but at the same time the olefin yield drops by nearly 50%.

The results of experiments carried out at 500° and space velocity 2hr⁻¹ with solutions of n-heptane containing different quantities of nhc compounds alone or as mixtures, are given in Fig. 1. & 2. Figures give

Fig. 1. Plot of selectivity V/S g-atom of nhe/ 100 ml feed.

- ⊙ n-butylamine (BA)
- Dimethylformamide (DMF)
- △ Furfural (FR)
- Propyl mercaptan (PM)

Fig. 2. Plot of selectivity V/S g-gtom of nhe/100 ml. feed.

- ⊙ Furfural + Propylmercaptan (FR) + (PM)
- ⊗ Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)
- ▽ Dimethylsulfoxide + n-butylamine (DMSO) + (BA)
- Dimethylsulfoxide + Furfural (DMSO) + (FR)

plot of selectivity defined as above versus concentration of total nonhydrocarbon in g-atom of nhe/100ml. feed. It is seen from the figures that the selectivity depends on the type of the nonhydrocarbon compounds and its concentration. While presence of small amount of PM improves the selectivity, larger amounts decrease

the value much more. Selectivity is improved by BA, DMSO and considerably by FR. In all these three cases, the value is highest at an optimum concentration. Selectivity is raised to the highest possible value, namely 1, by DMF and mixtures of DMSO+FR, PM + FR. Mixtures of DMSO+BA have little effect. The value of selectivity does not seem to be affected by the composition of the mixtures in the range studied.

Table—4 gives the value of the highest selectivity for the various cases and the corresponding olefin and aromatic yields. Comparison of Tables 3 and 4 shows interesting results. Although the improvement of the value of selectivity (in the absence of additive) is accompanied by decrease in olefin yield, the decrease is much less than in the case where improvement of selectivity is sought by change of kinetic parameters. Further, in several cases, selectivity improvement can be achieved even with increase in olefin yield. Presence of mixtures of FR + PM gives not only the highest value of selectivity, but also marginal improvement in olefin yield.

The question arises as to whether the presence of these compounds causes any permanent damage to intrinsic activity of the catalyst. In order to verify this aspect, runs were carried out with pure n-heptane at 500° and space velocity 2 hr⁻¹ at frequent intervals in the series of runs with n-heptane containing various nhc. It is seen from Table—5 that the presence of all nhc except PM does not affect the intrinsic activity or selectivity of the catalyst. However results of run number 62 show that PM damages activity permanently. Series of runs with mixtures of PM+FR were therefore carried out with a fresh sample of the catalyst. It is seen from the table that yields of olefins and aromatics in run 67, are only marginally less than those in run 29 or 58. This indicates that the presence of FR along with PM almost suppresses the poisoning action of the latter compound.

In figures 3,4,5, are plotted variation of selectivity with total concentration of S, O, and N in the feed solution. Fig. 3 shows that increase in sulphur content in solution causes only a mild increase in selectivity, there being an optimum value of S-content. However addition of oxygen to the solution at the same S conc. markedly improves the selectivity. The adverse influence of S is further verified by Fig. 4, since for the same concentration of oxygen in solution, presence of S depresses selectivity. Data for mixtures of DMSO + FR & PM + FR apparently seem to contradict this conclusion. If however the data corresponding to the highest concentration of FR alone in soln. is regarded as an error, this contradiction disappears. Further Fig. 4, shows that the selectivity may be taken broadly to increase with oxygen content upto approximately 0.05 g-atom of O/100 ml. feed and to remain at the highest value with further increase. Fig. 5 shows that presence of N in solution improves selectivity little. In fact larger quantities diminish the value. Fig. 5 also shows that addition of S and O along with N does not improve the selectivity as in the case of addition of oxygen to solution containing

TABLE - 4. CONDITIONS FOR HIGHEST SELECTIVITY

Reaction Temp. : 500°C ; Space velocity 2hr⁻¹

Type of nhc	Conc. in g-atom of nhe/100ml. feed.	Selectivity	Conversion		Catalyzate Olefin content in mole fraction
			Olefin	Aromatics	
—	0.0	0.49	0.076	0.079	0.092
BA.	0.029	0.61	0.064	0.040	0.077
DMSO	0.063	0.636	0.093	0.053	0.111
FR	0.044	0.84	0.058	0.011	0.075
DMF	0.066	1.0	0.065	0.0	0.076
PM	0.0016	0.56	0.088	0.08	0.118
BA + DMSO (1.4ml. + 2.26ml.)	0.078	0.568	0.075	0.057	0.098
DMSO + FR (2.25ml. + 1.85ml.)	0.081	0.972	0.064	0.002	0.075
FR + PM (3.17ml. + 2.6ml.)	0.106	1.0	0.082	0.0	0.104

TABLE - 5. EFFECT OF PRESENCE OF NONHYDROCARBON COMPOUNDS ON INTRINSIC ACTIVITY OF CATALYST.

Reaction Temp. : 500°C ; Space Velocity : 2 hr⁻¹

Run No.	29	35	41	45	50B	54	58	62	67
nhc Compounds in preceding runs	—	BA	DMSO	BA + DMSO	FR	FR + DMSO	DMF	PM	PM + FR
Conversion									
1) Olefins	0.075	0.077	0.075	0.076	0.075	0.076	0.076	0.024	0.069
2) Aromatics	0.079	0.076	0.079	0.077	0.079	0.077	0.077	0.036	0.063
Selectivity	0.487	0.504	0.487	0.498	0.486	0.498	0.498	0.400	0.524

S. Data with DMF alone showing beneficial influence of addition of O to solution, is not sufficient to come to any definite conclusion.

n-heptane containing the non-hydrocarbon compound but without any catalyst in the reactor. The results are given in Table 6.

The role of non-catalytic reactions, if any, in improving selectivity was tested by carrying out runs with

Comparison of Table 4 & 6 shows that in the presence of catalyst the aromatic yield is reduced to

TABLE-6. ROLE OF NON CATALYTIC REACTIONS

Reaction Temp. 500°C; Flow Rate—66 ml./hr.

Comp. of Sol.	Total Conversion		Non-catalytic Conversion above the catalyst bed.
	Olefin	Aromatic	Olefin
	0.004	0.024	0.002
1.85 ml. FR	0.031	0.039	0.01
0.52 ml. PM	0.028	0.028	0.01
3.15 ml. DMSO	0.024	0.047	0.009
1.8 ml. DMSO + 1.32 ml. FR	0.027	0.024	0.009
3.17 ml. FR + 2.6 ml. PM	0.02	0.039	0.007
1.07 ml. DMF	0.022	0.036	0.007

Fig. 3. Plot of selectivity V/S g-atom of S/100 ml. feed.

- ⊗ Furfural + Propylmercaptan (FR) + (PM)
- ⊙ Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)
- ⊖ Dimethylsulfoxide + n-butylamine (DMSO) + (BA)
- ⊕ Propyl mercaptan (PM)
- Dimethylsulfoxide + Furfural (DMSO) + (FR)

Fig. 4. Plot of selectivity V/S g-atom of O/100 ml. feed.

- ⊗ Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)
- ⊙ Furfural + Propylmercaptan (FR) + (PM)
- ⊖ Furfural (FR)
- ⊕ Dimethylsulfoxide + n-butylamine (DMSO) + (BA)
- ⊖ Dimethylformamide (DMF)
- Dimethylsulfoxide + Furfural (DMSO) + (FR)

Fig. 5. Plot of selectivity V/S g-atom of N/100 ml. feed.

- ⊙ n-butylamine (BA)
- ⊖ Dimethylsulfoxide + n-butylamine (DMSO) + (BA)
- ⊖ Dimethylformamide (DMF)

zero, although the noncatalytic reaction should yield a minimum value of 0.03. This is possible under the following circumstances :

- a) Formation of aromatic and olefin from paraffin is a reaction of type $P \rightarrow O \rightarrow A$, or the yield of aromatic with increase of reciprocal space velocity shows an induction period.
- b) In the presence of the catalyst the non-catalytic contribution is negligible.
- c) Conversion of olefin to aromatic is inhibited by the catalyst, and
- d) The olefin content at the end of catalyst bed has reached pseudo equilibrium value so that it undergoes little further change before leaving the reactor. (This possibility is indicated by data in Table 3).

In other words the non-catalytic contribution would only be due to portion of the reactor above the catalyst bed only. In order to estimate this value, the equivalent reactor volume¹⁵ for non-catalytic reactions at 500°, was calculated from the axial temperature profile of the reactor, and literature values on kinetic data for thermal cracking of n-heptane¹⁶ and the fraction of this volume above the catalyst bed was estimated. Conversion in this equivalent reactor volume fraction, was estimated by assuming the noncatalytic reaction to be first order and conversion to be linear with reciprocal space velocity. The results of such calculations are given in Table-6. It is seen from Table-6, that contribution of noncatalytic reaction to olefins is more or less within experimental error. For this reason the olefin yields obtained in this investigation may be regarded as entirely catalytic.

The rate controlling step in the above reactions may be taken as surface reaction in view of pronounced influence of the additives in the feed on the extent of dehydrogenation. This was confirmed by estimating

the extent of external mass transfer control by conventional methods¹⁷. These calculations indicate that at 500°, space velocity 2hr⁻¹ a maximum catalyst bed height of 1.4 cms. is only required to achieve 100% conversion of n-heptane fed. The maximum conversion obtained in the various runs with catalyst bed height of 2 cms. did not exceed 30%. Similarly pore diffusion limitations would be negligible since for industrial chromia-alumina catalyst the effectiveness factor is 0.7¹⁸.

As mentioned in the introduction the nhc compounds were expected to modify the acidity of the catalyst surface. A measure of the extent of this modification by the compounds may be their pK_a values. Literature information indicates that such values are reported for only a few of the compounds : BA : 10.77 at 20°; DMSO : 1.4 at 22°; DMF : -0.01 at 20°¹⁹. It is seen that the magnitude of these values has no relation to the role of the compounds in improving selectivity. This is not surprising, since as mentioned above, data in Table-1 indicate possibility of decomposition of the compounds under the experimental conditions. This is again supported by literature information which indicates possibility of decomposition of DMSO to methyl-mercaptan and bismethylthiomethane²⁰; PM to olefin and H₂S²¹; DMF to dimethylamine and carbon monoxide²²; and FR to various acids²³. Improvement of the selectivity in the presence of nhc compounds may therefore involve modification of catalyst surface acidity on account of a number of complex compounds. The elucidation of this phenomenon is not possible without further detailed work.

The olefin yield obtained in this work may be regarded as low but as Table-4 indicates catalyzate olefin content in mole fraction could be of the order of 0.1. This may not be a disadvantage in further exploitation of the catalyzate in cases, such as polymerization carried out in the presence of a paraffin as inert diluent²⁴.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank W. G. Grace & Co., Baltimore, U.S.A. for gift of the chromia-alumina catalyst, and to Shri V. R. Khorgade, M.Sc., M.Tech. for his help in the initial stages of the experimental work.

References

1. UOP, Methods makes linear detergent alkylate. *Chemical Engg. News*, 1966, 44 (51), 78.

2. MOLEX PROCESS, *Hydrocarbon Processing*, 1972, 51 (9), 214.
3. D. B. BROUGHTON, *Chem. Engg. Prog.*, 1968, 64 (8), 60.
4. W. J. ASCHER, M. L. CAMPBELL and W. R. EPPERLY, *Hydrocarbon Processing*, 1969, 48 (1), 134.
5. PACOL-OLEX PROCESS, *Hydrocarbon Processing*, 1973, 52 (11), 145.
6. N. I. SHUILKIN, E. A. THIMOFFEVA and V. S. SMIRNOV, *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 63, 17830C.
7. B. A. DADASHEV, L. S. MUSTAFAEV and P. M. POLADOV, *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 65, 8739e.
8. J. F. ROTH, J. B. ABELL and A. R. SCHAEFER, *I & E. C. Prod. & Res. Dev.*, 1968, 7, 254.
9. J. F. ROTH, R. ANDREW and A. R. SCHAEFER, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 61445z.
10. J. HUGHES, *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 65, 2123h.
11. N. I. SHUILKIN, E. A. THIMOFFEVA and V. S. SMIRNOV, 'Proceedings of the Third International Congress on Catalysis', North-Holland Publishing Co., New York, 1965, 1, 495.
12. J. MASSON and B. DELMON, 'Proceedings of 5th International Congress on Catalysis', by J. W. HIGHTOWER, North Holland Publishing Co., New York, 1973, 1, 6-183.
13. B. A. KAZANSKII, M. I. ROZENGAVT and E. F. KUZNETSOVA, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. USSR.*, 1959, 787, 126.
14. I. P. Standards for Petroleum and its Products, Institute of Petroleum, U. K. 33rd Ed. Applied Science Publishers, Part-I, 1974, 468, 554.
15. G. FORMENT, H. PICKE and G. GOETHALS, *Chem. Engg. Sci.*, 1961, 13 (3), 180.
16. B. M. FABUSS, J. O. SMITH and S. N. SATTERFIELD, *Advances in Petroleum Chemistry and Refining*, Interscience, New York, Edited by J. J. MCKETTA, 1964, 9, 180.
17. A. JAIN, M. Tech. Thesis submitted to Nagpur University 1975.
18. C. N. SATTERFIELD, *Mass transfer in heterogeneous catalysis*, M. I. T. Press, London, 1970, 153.
19. J. A. RIDDICK and W. B. BUNGER, 'Organic Solvents—Physical Properties and Methods of Purification', Wiley-Interscience, New York, 3rd Ed., 1970, Vol. II, 418, 446, 466, 486.
20. J. VICENT, TRAYNELIS and L. WILLIAM HERGENROTHER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 221.
21. W. M. MALISOFF and E. M. MARKS, *Ind. Engg. Chem.*, 1931, 23 (10), 1114.
22. Ref. 19, P. 837.
23. Ref. 19, P. 869.
24. KERK OTHMER, Interscience Publishers, *Enc. of Chem. Tech.*, 1963, 1, 566.